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TIMEPIX4 TIMING LAYER IN TELESCOPES

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Abstract:

The Timepix4 timing layers provide sub-nanosecond track time to the EUDET-style beam telescopes. This document reports on the design of the Timepix4 based timing layers, which constitutes MS9 in month 42.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2024

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Executive summary

Timing layers with sub-nanosecond time resolution are based on the Timepix4 ASIC, which has been developed by the Medipix4 consortium of which Nikhef is a partner, and therefore access to this technology. Timepix4 is designed in 65 nm CMOS technology and has 512×448 square pixels at a 55 μm pitch and has a per-pixel Time to Digital converter with 195 picosecond bins.

The sensors for the timing layers are provided via WP6 and with 300 μm n-on-p planar sensors a time resolution well below 1 ns can be achieved. To control the Timepix4 chip and acquire its data, the SPIDR4 readout system has been developed. This system, based on a Xilinx Zync 7000 series FPGA is capable of reading out the Timepix4 chip and send its data to a 10 Gbit ethernet network with a hit rate in excess of 100 million hits per second. Due to the late delivery of the sensors, the timing performance of the Timepix4 and the validation of the SPIDR4 readout system have been done with sensors from a non-AIDAinnova, project. Multiple tests of the full readout chain and the validation of the time resolution of the complete system have been performed with charged particle beams at CERN. Integration of the DAQ and control software into the EUDAQ2 framework is nearing completion.

1. INTRODUCTION

Within AIDAinnova WP3 the development of detection layers with sub-nanosecond time precision is pursued. These Timepix4 [1] based timing layers complement the existing EUDET-style telescopes, which provide an excellent spatial resolution but lack sufficient time resolution. Being highly granular, the Timepix4 provides sufficient spatial resolution such that each reconstructed track can be linked to the time measurement in the offline track reconstruction. The extra time information enhances the telescope's capabilities, allowing characterisation of devices-under-test with fast timing capabilities, even at high beam rates. This report focuses on the development and performance validation of the timing layers, its readout system, and the integration into the EUDET telescopes [2].

2. DESIGN OF TIMEPIX4 TIMING LAYER AND SPIDR4 READOUT

2.1. TIMEPIX4 PIXEL ASIC

The heart of the timing layer is the Timepix4, which is a readout ASIC for hybrid pixel sensors, which is developed by the Medipix4 consortium [1]. Timepix4 is designed in a 65 nm CMOS technology and has 512×448 square pixels at a $55 \mu\text{m}$ pitch. The first version of the chip (v0) was submitted late 2019 and since then three versions (v1, v2, v3) have been submitted to fix bugs and improve performance. Early access to this technology was possible because of NWO-I/Nikhef's active role in the development of the ASIC.

Figure 1. Timepix4 on a SPIDR4 chipboard (left), zoomed version (right) showing the hybrid structure with sensor on top of the Timepix4 ASIC.

The Timepix4, shown in Fig.1, can measure the time-of-arrival and the time-over-threshold simultaneously in each pixel, and the least-significant bit of the time-to-digital converter has a nominal size of 195 ps. The time performance of the hybrid assembly depends significantly on the type and thickness of the sensor mounted on the Timepix4 ASIC. Moreover, to achieve the optimal time resolution careful tuning of the parameters in the ASIC is required, and offline per-pixel correction factors to equalise the performance need to be determined. This will be explained in more detail in section 3.

Given the late arrival of the sensors from WP6, the flip-chipped detector assemblies only became available in M41. Hence all tests have been done with a sensor borrowed from another, non-AIDAinnova, project. Similar results are expected for the $300 \mu\text{m}$ sensor assemblies that arrived recently.

2.2. SPIDR4 READOUT SYSTEM

A readout system called SPIDR4 (Speedy Pixel Detector Readout, generation 4) [3] has been developed in parallel with the Timepix4 ASIC. The system is modular and consists of three different types of boards: a chip carrier board, a Control board that also takes care of DAQ with rates of up to 10 Gbit/s, and a high-rate DAQ board that can deal with the full 160 Gbit/s bandwidth of Timepix4. For most applications, including the timing layers for the AIDAinnova beam telescopes, the high rate

DAQ board is not needed as the Control board is sufficient for detector hit rates up to about 100 MHz. Figure 2 shows the SPIDR4 configuration that is used for the beam telescopes, and all its interfaces.

Figure 2. SPIDR4 readout system, consisting of the chipboard with the Timepix4 ASIC and the Control Board that takes care of the DAQ over 10 Gbit ethernet.

The SPIDR4 control board receives the data from the Timepix4 chip and packs it into UDP datagrams and subsequently sends it over 10 Gbit/s ethernet to the data acquisition computer. The configuration of the Timepix4, the FPGA parameters and the monitoring of temperatures, power, etc. is done via a 1 Gbit ethernet connection. All communication is based on the gRPC protocol which makes the controls language independent. The SPIDR4 and subsequently the Timepix4 (can) run on an external 40 MHz clock that will be provided by the AIDAinnova Trigger Logic Unit (TLU), thereby ensuring synchronous operation with the rest of the telescope. The system also responds to the other control signals (T0-reset, shutter) provided by the TLU.

Although in the prototyping phase, the production of the boards was severely delayed because of the global supply chain issues (due to Covid); the delay has been recovered in the testing phase and both the carrier board and control board have been produced and tested successfully.

2.3. MECHANICS AND INTEGRATION

The Timepix4 timing layers have to be integrated into the existing mechanical infrastructure of the telescope and therefore a custom-made support plate has been designed and produced. The plate, shown in Fig.3, is compatible with the mounting rail system of the telescope, and allows for a quick

replacement of a timing layer, if needed. Because the silicon sensors are light sensitive a 3D printed shielding and protection cap is placed over (only) the Timepix4 assembly.

Figure 3. Timing layer including mechanical structure and light tight sensor protection cover.

On the software side the integration of the timing layers into the EUDAQ2 framework [4] is nearing completion. In more detail, the Producer code exists and the embedding into the framework is being tested, see Fig.4. Similarly, on the data acquisition side the Data Collector code is ready and framework integration is being finalized. The formatted data will be passed to the File Writer in straight-to-disk mode and linked to the reconstructed tracks offline.

Figure 4. Screenshot showing that communication between the Producer (tpx4sc, background) and the EUDAQ Run Control (front panel) has been established.

3. VALIDATION OF TIMING PERFORMANCE WITH CHARGED PARTICLES

The time resolution of the Timepix4 sensor assembly depends not only on the binning of the time-to-digital in the ASIC, but also on the jitter in the analog front-end, the amount of signal that the sensor provides and especially the charge collection time (or more precisely, the magnitude of the induced current). Hence different sensor types require a different optimisation of the front-end in Timepix4 (such as threshold and preamplifier current) to achieve the best performance. But even with the optimised ASIC settings, the out-of-box time resolution is sub-optimal and further improvements, up to a factor two, depending on sensor type, can be achieved. The two most obvious corrections needed are time walk, which is the effect that larger signals cross the threshold earlier, and the determination of the frequency of the local clock in the chip. In the Timepix4, each group of 8 pixels has its own Voltage Controlled Oscillator (VCO, nominal frequency 640 MHz) that is switched on when a particle hits the pixel, and switched off on the next rising edge of the clock to reduce the power consumption. The control voltage of the VCO is obtained from a reference VCO in the periphery of the chip, which is locked to the central 40 MHz clock and hence runs at exactly 640 MHz. However, VCOs in the pixel are not identical due to process variations. Moreover, the supply voltage and even temperature of the local VCO is slightly different and hence the frequency can deviate. Figure 5 (left) shows a typical distribution of the VCO frequency across the matrix of the Timepix4. The distribution is determined using a statistical method and a radioactive source data and is cross-checked with charged particle beams in a telescope like configuration similar to [5], but now with two MCP-PMT detectors as time reference.

Figure 5. (left) Typical VCO frequency variation across the matrix of Timepix4. (right) Typical time walk curve for a single pixel of Timepix4 with a 100 μm sensor.

The right side of Fig.5 shows an example of the time walk in Timepix4 for a 100 μm thick sensor. Time walk can, to a large extent, be corrected with the ToT information. However, the exact shape of the time walk curve depends on the sensor, front-end setting and to obtain the best time resolution, per-pixel correction parameters must be determined.

Figure 6. (left) Time residual distribution after time walk and VCO corrections. The sensor was a 100 μm thick n-on-p planar sensor.

In a beam test at the SPS H8 beam line, a time resolution of about 150 ps for a 100 μm thick planar n-on-p sensor has been obtained after time walk and VCO corrections. As shown by Fig.6. the VCO corrections give a large improvement in this case because the beam was in the centre of the sensor, where the VCOs run slowest (see Fig 5, left). With the 300 μm sensor that became available last month a slightly worse time resolution is expected. Even though the sensor is thicker and hence provides a larger signal, one cannot profit from this because of the small pixel pitch, which implies a very peaked weighting field near the pixel implants. With the 3D and LGAD devices developed within WP6, a somewhat better time resolution than for a 100 μm thick sensor is expected.

4. REFERENCES

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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
CMOS	Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor
DAQ	Data Acquisition
SPIDR4	Speedy Pixel Detector Readout system
ToA	Time of Arrival
ToT	Time over Threshold
TLU	Trigger Logic Unit
VCO	Voltage Controlled Oscillator